

Delphi study on barriers to the implementation of a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline – results from Bulgaria

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Abstract

Although postgraduate training in clinical pharmacy has been established in Bulgaria since 1986, the practical implementation and standardization of clinical pharmacy practice remain insufficiently studied and documented. This Delphi study explored barriers to introducing a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline. Eight clinical pharmacists from six university hospitals identified, ranked, and prioritized barriers. A total of 12 barriers were categorized into educational, regulatory, logistical, organizational, and financial groups. The most frequently cited barrier was the insufficient number of clinical pharmacists in hospital settings (87.5%). The most meaningful barriers were insufficient practical training during specialty education and the lack of a comprehensive regulatory framework. A moderate and statistically significant degree of concordance between the pharmacists was observed (Kendall's $W = 0.320$; $p = 0.003$). The findings highlight the need for targeted educational, regulatory, and workforce-related measures to ensure consistent and high-quality clinical pharmacy practice.

Keywords

Clinical pharmacy, clinical pharmacy practice, Delphi method, guideline, pharmaceutical practice

Introduction

The evolution of the pharmacy profession toward a clinically oriented model can be traced back to the mid-20th century, when professional focus gradually shifted from product-centered dispensing to patient-centered care. In Europe, the United Kingdom formally recognized clinical pharmacy as a specialty in 1989, followed by other European countries (Cotter 1995). Since then, the concept of clinical pharmacy practice has expanded considerably. However, owing to structural and conceptual differences among national healthcare systems, its scope and implementation have evolved in response to local needs and regulatory

contexts. Although the European Society of Clinical Pharmacy (ESCP) and the European Association of Hospital Pharmacists (EAHP) have published guidance and strategic documents outlining the advancement of clinical pharmacy practice, these remain advisory in nature. Consequently, the development, organization, and extent of clinical pharmacy practice continue to depend largely on national educational policies and regulatory frameworks.

In Bulgaria, postgraduate specialty training in clinical pharmacy has been available since 1986 (Getov 2015). Despite this long-standing educational foundation, the implementation and integration of clinical pharmacy practice in hospital settings remain insufficiently studied

and poorly documented. The absence of a formal regulatory framework prior to 2019 likely contributed to the limited evaluation and standardization of clinical practice. Moreover, the factors underlying historically modest institutional and professional engagement in this field have not been comprehensively examined. Since 2015, the introduction of a revised postgraduate specialty curriculum—currently in force—has been associated with renewed professional interest in clinical pharmacy. In parallel, forthcoming national educational reforms are expected to establish Clinical Pharmacy as a mandatory standalone discipline within undergraduate pharmacy education, further strengthening the academic basis of the specialty (Commission Delegated Directive (EU) 2024/782, European Commission 2024).

Nevertheless, current regulatory provisions, which require the presence of at least one clinical pharmacist in certain hospital settings (e.g., oncology and hematology units), do not ensure the delivery of comprehensive, high-quality clinical pharmacy services. Bulgaria has not yet adopted a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline. Moreover, only limited provisions are included in the Rules of Good Pharmaceutical Practice (2020). This regulatory gap allows variability in the scope and quality of pharmaceutical care and may contribute to ambiguity in professional roles and responsibilities. In that sense, the establishment of a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline would provide a structured framework for defining professional competencies, responsibilities, and quality benchmarks, thereby promoting consistency and sustainability in service delivery.

The aim of this study was to identify and analyze the principal barriers to the development and implementation of a unified national clinical pharmacy practice guideline in Bulgaria.

Materials and methods

Study design

The study employed a single-round modified Delphi method for structured expert consultation. Although multiple variations of this methodology exist, the study adhered to its core principles: anonymity, iteration with controlled feedback, statistical aggregation of group responses, and expert input to achieve consensus (Hasson et al. 2025). Although the panel size was relatively small ($n = 8$), this is consistent with methodological recommendations for Delphi studies involving highly specialized expert groups (Okoli and Pawlowski 2004; Hsu and Sandford 2007). Future research could incorporate multiple iterative rounds with controlled feedback to further strengthen consensus.

Expert panel selection

Data were collected from experts working in hospital healthcare institutions in Bulgaria. The respondents met at least one of the criteria defined in the current regulatory framework requiring the presence of a clinical pharmacist

practicing in the specialty. The criteria for selecting the participants in the expert panel were as follows:

1. Master's degree in Pharmacy.
2. Completed postgraduate specialty training in Clinical Pharmacy.
3. Minimum of 5 years of professional experience as a clinical pharmacist.
4. At least 5 years of hospital-based practice.
5. Experience in supervising undergraduate pharmacy trainees.

Data collection

Data were collected through structured face-to-face interviews consisting of three components:

- An open-ended question identifying barriers.
- A ranking question, ordering barriers by importance.
- A prioritization question identifying the single most critical barrier.

Open-ended question

“What do you consider to be the main barriers to the implementation of a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline?”

This question was designed to elicit unrestricted expert perspectives and directly address the primary objective of the study.

Ranking question

“Please rank the barriers you identified in order of importance, starting with the most important.”

This task enabled the relative comparison and hierarchical ordering of the identified barriers. The participants ranked only the barriers they had identified in the open-ended phase.

Prioritization question

“Please indicate the single most important barrier that, in your opinion, if addressed, would contribute the most to the successful implementation of a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline.”

This question was intended to identify the primary barrier as a focal point for further consideration and policy attention.

Demographic data were collected, including age, sex, number of years since obtaining the specialty in clinical pharmacy, and years of professional practice or experience in the specialty. The study aim and design were explained to all participants in advance, and written informed consent was obtained prior to participation. No personal data falling within the scope of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) were collected. Although interviews were conducted face-to-face, responses were anonymized during data processing, and participants were not aware of the identities or responses of other panel members. According to national

regulations (Medicinal Products in Human Medicine Act), formal ethical approval was not required for this type of expert-based, anonymous, non-interventional study.

Limitations and justification of the sample size

The expert panel was limited to clinical pharmacists practicing in university hospitals in the capital, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other regions or healthcare settings nationally. We also acknowledge that the conditions and contextual characteristics of the settings in which these experts practice may have influenced the ranking of the identified barriers. However, they likely had a lesser effect on the selection of the barriers themselves and on identifying the most significant among them.

According to available national data, the number of clinical pharmacists with a postgraduate specialty in Bulgaria remains limited (approximately 100 professionals), and only a proportion are currently practicing in hospital settings, with a high concentration in Sofia. Although recent regulatory changes allow pharmacists with undergraduate training in clinical pharmacy to practice in hospital settings, their uptake of clinical pharmacist roles appears to remain limited. In this context, the use of a relatively small expert panel is justified and consistent with methodological recommendations for Delphi studies involving highly specialized groups (Okoli and Pawlowski 2004; Hsu and Sandford 2007).

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 29. Results are presented as absolute and relative frequencies for categorical variables and as means with standard deviations (SD) for continuous variables. Normality was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. The degree of concordance among experts was evaluated using Kendall's coefficient of concordance (W). Mean ranks and relative importance were calculated to further describe the results. The relative importance, as a measure of the consensus level, was calculated as the mean rank divided by the maximal rank. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Data were collected from eight (8) clinical pharmacists employed at six (6) university multispecialty hospitals in Sofia, Bulgaria. The mean age of participants was 52 years (SD 6.33), and the mean duration of their professional practice as clinical pharmacists was 16.63 years (SD 9.13). Most participants had been continuously practicing as clinical pharmacists since obtaining their certification, with a mean duration of 14.63 years (SD 8.50). Seven participants were female (87.5%) and one was male (12.5%) (Table 1).

A total of 12 distinct barriers were identified (5.38 per participant). The most frequently cited barrier was "Insufficient number of clinical pharmacists working in hospital settings" (87.5%) (Table 2).

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the expert participants.

Expert	Age	Sex	Year of specialty certification in Clinical Pharmacy	Years of professional experience after specialty certification in Clinical Pharmacy in hospital	Years of clinical pharmacy practice with defined clinical responsibilities
A	65	female	1996	33	29
B	49	male	2015	10	7
C	55	female	2001	24	24
D	55	female	2006	19	13
E	49	female	2007	18	18
F	47	female	2020	5	5
G	51	female	2017	8	8
H	45	female	2009	16	13

Table 2. Barriers to the implementation of a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline and their frequency of occurrence.

Category	Barrier	Frequency of mention (n)	Number of first-place rankings (n)	Mean rank	Relative importance (%)
Logistical	Insufficient number of clinical pharmacists working in hospital settings.	7	1	3.75	62.50%
	Limited acceptance of clinical pharmacists by medical teams and hospital administration.	6	1	1.75	29.17%
	Inadequate working conditions	4	0	1.75	29.17%
	Lack of established collaboration between pharmacists and physicians.	1	0	0.38	6.33%
Organizational	Lack of initiative to develop a national clinical pharmacy practice standard.	3	1	2.00	33.33%
	Lack of a unified professional position among clinical pharmacists.	2	0	0.63	10.50%
	Insufficient evidence demonstrating the benefits of clinical pharmacy practice.	2	0	0.88	14.67%
Educational	Insufficient practical training of clinical pharmacists during specialty education.	6	2	3.88	64.67%
	Lack of professional confidence among clinical pharmacists.	1	0	0.50	8.33%
Regulatory	Lack of a comprehensive regulatory framework for clinical pharmacy practice or insufficient enforcement of existing regulations.	4	2	2.63	43.83%
	Lack of administrative will and implementation capacity.	1	0	0.38	6.33%
Financial	Low remuneration of pharmacists working in hospital settings.	5	1	2.00	33.33%

The barriers receiving the highest number of first-place rankings (two each) were “Insufficient practical training of clinical pharmacists during specialty education” and “Lack of a comprehensive regulatory framework for clinical pharmacy practice or insufficient enforcement of existing regulations.” Kendall’s coefficient of concordance demonstrated a moderate and statistically significant degree of concordance among the experts ($W = 0.320$; $p = 0.003$).

To determine relative priority, numerical ranks were assigned according to expert ordering. A barrier placed first received a rank of 6, whereas a barrier placed sixth received a rank of 1. Barriers not mentioned were assigned a rank of 0. The ranks were summed and averaged across participants (Table 2). The highest-ranked barrier was “Insufficient practical training of clinical pharmacists during specialty education” (mean rank 3.88; relative importance 64.67%), followed by “Insufficient number of clinical pharmacists working in hospital settings” (mean rank 3.75; relative importance 62.5%). The lowest-ranked barrier was “Lack of administrative will and implementation capacity” (mean rank 0.38; relative importance 6.33%).

The identified barriers were classified into five main categories: logistical, organizational, educational, regulatory, and financial.

Figure 1. Distribution of barrier categories by frequency of mention. This figure presents the aggregated distribution of barriers across five categories: logistical, organizational, educational, regulatory, and financial. In contrast to Table 2, which provides detailed information on individual barriers, this figure summarizes their overall distribution at the category level. The logistical category accounted for the highest proportion of mentions (33.33%), including insufficient number of clinical pharmacists working in hospital settings, limited acceptance by medical teams and hospital administration, and inadequate working conditions. Educational and regulatory categories were also prominent, whereas organizational and financial categories were less frequently reported.

Table 3. Most important barrier to address according to the experts and its relative importance.

Expert	Most important barrier to address
A, B, C	Insufficient practical training of clinical pharmacists during specialty education.
D, E, F	Lack of a comprehensive regulatory framework for clinical pharmacy practice or insufficient enforcement of existing regulations.
G	Insufficient number of clinical pharmacists working in hospital settings.
H	Lack of a unified professional position regarding the need for a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline.

and financial. The logistical category accounted for the greatest proportion of mentions (18 mentions; 33.33%) (Table 2; Fig. 1). This category included working conditions, the insufficient number of clinical pharmacists, interactions with medical staff, and other related factors.

Experts ranked the barriers according to importance (Fig. 2), with six of the 12 identified barriers (50%) designated as the most important by at least one expert.

In the prioritization phase, four barriers were identified as most important to address. “Insufficient practical training of clinical pharmacists during specialty education” and “Lack of a comprehensive regulatory framework for clinical pharmacy practice or insufficient enforcement of existing regulations” were considered equally critical, each receiving three leading responses (Table 3).

Discussion

This Delphi study provides a structured expert-based assessment of barriers to the implementation of a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline in Bulgaria. The findings indicate that the challenges are multifactorial, with

Figure 2. Ranking of barriers according to expert-assigned importance. This figure presents the ranking of identified barriers according to expert assessment. Each row represents an individual expert and each column a barrier category. Marked cells indicate the barrier selected as the top priority by a given expert, illustrating the distribution of expert opinions. The barrier names are shortened in the figure for readability. Full descriptions are as follows: Training – “Insufficient practical training of clinical pharmacists during specialty education”; Regulation – “Lack of a comprehensive regulatory framework for clinical pharmacy practice or insufficient enforcement of existing regulations”; Workforce – “Insufficient number of clinical pharmacists working in hospital settings”; Acceptance – “Limited acceptance of clinical pharmacists by medical teams and hospital administration”; Remuneration – “Low remuneration of pharmacists working in hospital settings”; Administration – “Lack of administrative will and implementation capacity.” Six of the 12 barriers (50%) were designated as most important by at least one expert. The highest mean ranks were observed for “Insufficient practical training of clinical pharmacists during specialty education” and “Lack of a comprehensive regulatory framework for clinical pharmacy practice or insufficient enforcement of existing regulations”. Kendall’s coefficient indicated a moderate and statistically significant degree of concordance ($W = 0.320$; $p = 0.003$).

educational, regulatory, and logistical factors emerging as the most influential. The statistically significant value of Kendall's coefficient demonstrated a moderate degree of concordance among expert opinions, supporting both the reliability of the findings and the appropriateness of the chosen methodological approach.

No single dominant barrier was identified when considering either the ranking results or the prioritization responses independently. Despite the established regulatory structure in the country and the development of postgraduate specialty training in clinical pharmacy, experts emphasized a persistent gap between theoretical instruction and practical application, which reflects a broader issue recognized in international literature. Insufficient experiential training may limit professional confidence (also noted by one participant), clinical decision-making capacity, and effective participation in multidisciplinary teams. A survey commissioned by the ESCP similarly highlighted the importance of structured practical training in supporting the expanding role of clinical pharmacists, as well as residency-type models (Bond and Raehl 2007; Moura et al. 2022). This suggests that strengthening experiential learning should be a priority in clinical pharmacy education. The existing experienced clinical pharmacy workforce in university hospitals could be utilized to support the practical training of clinical pharmacy students. Regulatory barriers were also identified as central determinants. Although a regulatory framework is currently in place, experts indicated that it remains insufficiently comprehensive and could be further strengthened. The emphasis placed on regulatory deficiencies underscores the need for the establishment of a formal framework that clearly defines the scope of practice, professional responsibilities, and quality requirements for clinical pharmacy practice in Bulgaria. Similar challenges have been reported in other European settings, where the absence of clearly defined practice standards contributes to variability in service delivery and professional roles (Schumock et al. 2003; EAHP 2014). Several of these deficiencies could be addressed through the adoption of a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline.

Despite formal compliance with existing regulatory requirements, experts considered current workforce capacity inadequate to ensure sustainable and comprehensive clinical pharmacy services. This finding suggests that minimum regulatory requirements may not adequately reflect the actual demands of clinical practice and that workforce planning should account for the complexity and intensity of service provision. This observation is consistent with European workforce analyses, which indicate that staffing levels often remain insufficient to support comprehensive clinical pharmacy practice (EAHP 2014). Addressing this gap will require strategic workforce planning that reflects the complexity and scope of clinical pharmacy activities. In this context, recent regulatory changes allowing pharmacists with undergraduate training in clinical pharmacy to practice in hospital settings may support workforce expansion. However, the distinction in roles and responsibilities between these practitioners and those with post-

graduate specialty qualifications remains unclear and requires further clarification.

Although logistical barriers were the most numerous, they, together with organizational barriers, were ranked lower in relative priority compared to educational and regulatory factors. This pattern suggests that strengthening practical training and establishing clear professional standards may facilitate better integration of clinical pharmacists within hospital processes. Evidence from other healthcare systems indicates that clearly defined professional roles are associated with improved interprofessional collaboration (Makowsky et al. 2009).

Financial constraints, such as low remuneration of pharmacists working in hospital settings, were acknowledged but were not identified as primary barriers by the expert panel. This may indicate that structural and professional determinants currently play a more significant role in limiting the development of clinical pharmacy practice in Bulgaria.

The relatively low prioritization of administrative and implementation-related barriers suggests that the main challenges are perceived as internal to the profession rather than resulting from external resistance. This interpretation is further supported by the observation that some experts indicated a lack of a unified professional position regarding the need for a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline and suggests internal divergence surrounding future development within the field. This highlights the importance of professional consensus in driving policy development, potentially through the organization of clinical pharmacists into structured forums for coordinated discussion. Overcoming these barriers will require coordinated efforts among academic institutions, regulatory authorities, and professional organizations.

Conclusion

The implementation of a national clinical pharmacy practice guideline in Bulgaria should be accompanied by efforts to strengthen the practical components of specialty education, increase the number of clinical pharmacists working in hospital settings, and establish a clear and operational regulatory framework. Addressing these key determinants may create the conditions necessary to mitigate secondary organizational and financial barriers and to improve the quality, sustainability, and accessibility of clinical pharmacy services.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

All authors participated in the conduct of the study and preparation of the current manuscript, as follows: Conceptualization: SE, IG; Methodology: SE, EN, IG; Writing – original draft preparation: SE; Writing – review and editing: EN, VGK, IG; Visualization: SE, EN; Supervision: IG, VGK.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.